

MARKETING MODEL FOR THE PREVENTION OF YOUTHS INVOLVEMENT IN TERRORISTS ACTIVITIES IN NIGERIA.

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Abstract: *The rate of youth's involvement in terrorist activities in Nigeria is alarming. Many lives and properties are destroyed as a result, and the citizens live with perpetual fear. The purpose of this study is therefore to identify and explain a Marketing Model for the prevention of terrorist activities in Nigeria. A combination of Interview and Questionnaire methods were employed to elicit response from inmates of popular Correctional Centre. Data obtained was analysed through Descriptive Statistics. The findings include that: both male and female youths are involved in terrorist activities, but the male are more in number; most of the youths involved in terrorist activities have less than ordinary level education; the main causes of youth's involvement in terrorism are: peer group influence, poverty, high cost of acquiring education, unemployment, weak parental upbringing, insecurity in the country, religious and ethnic extremism; most of those involved in terrorism do not have knowledge of the consequences of the crime; and some of those involved in terrorism are indigenes of neighboring African countries. Based on the findings, this study recommends the application of a Marketing Model that comprise a sequence of marketing activities.*

Introduction

A terrorist is any person that is involved in executing terrorism. Terrorism is an act that connotes violence (terror) against individuals or the state. The aim of terrorism is to institute fear against the populace and possibly overtake a government or coerce government to implement

decisions according to the dictates of the terrorist group. The consequences of terrorism is death to the terrorist, innocent citizens and government (Ejeh, Bappah and Dankofa, 2019). Currently, the Nigeria nation is threatened by the spate terrorist's activities perpetrated by the youths.

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The situation in most worrisome because people no longer move freely in all parts of the country for fear of being attacked and kidnapped and huge amount of money demanded as ransom; most of the people kidnapped are gruesomely killed for their inability to pay ransom, while some are killed even after paying the ransom. Social-economic activities in the country are greatly threatened, government is spending huge amount of money for security, and many youths die as a result of their involvement in terrorist activities. The youths are referred to as the leaders of tomorrow, if the leaders of tomorrow are destroyed before the tomorrow, then the survival of this nation is threatened (Madu, 2018).

Some efforts have been made by the Government at various levels through security and other relevant agencies, religious institutions or organizations, traditional rulers and non-governmental organizations. Despite these efforts the menace of youth's involvement in terrorism still persist. This calls for the need to apply marketing approach as a strategic option for curbing youth's involvement in terrorist activities in Nigeria. The application or marketing extends to non-business activities. Marketing is an organized efforts to satisfy individual and organization needs for the purpose of realizing a long-lasting mutually benefiting relationships among the parties involved in the transaction (Madu, 2022). can be utilized to prevent youth's involvement in terrorists The purpose of this study is therefore

to identify and explain how Marketing activities activities in Nigeria.

Materials and Method

To realize the purpose of this study, the opinion of inmates in a popular correctional centre in Nigeria was obtained through an interview-aided questionnaire. The name of the correctional centre is withheld for security purposes and as directed by the management of the correctional centre. The data obtained was subjected to descriptive analysis, and the result employed for discussion of findings. Furthermore, studies related to the topic understudy were reviewed.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Marketing

The American Marketing Association as quoted in Jobber, 2004 gave a unifying definition of Marketing as “the process of planning and executing the conceptualization, pricing, promotion and distribution of ideas, goods and services to create changes that satisfy individual and organizational objectives”. The relevance of this definition emanates from its encompassing nature that adequately captures the meaning of Marketing which is aimed at realizing the objectives of the parties involved in the exchange relationships. Kotler and Armstrong, 2005 state that to realize the marketing objectives, a sequence of activities are required. These activities include that: the marketer must first identify the needs of the market and subsequently provide the goods, ideas or services that would satisfy the identified needs; the

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marketer must design a customer driven marketing strategy which is preceded by construction of a marketing programme that would deliver superior value; and all marketing efforts should be aimed at building profitable relationships and creating customer delight for attracting superior value to the marketing organization.

Relating the above definitions to our study, the implications and interpretation of marketing include that: the marketing organization is the government who is desirous of curbing youths involvement in terrorist activities as a result of its consequences; the customer is the youths whose needs is to avoid terrorism; the concept (Product) include the tangible and intangibles offers such as the goods, services and ideas by the government that must be offers to the youths to enable them avoid terrorism; prices is what the youths give in return (such as avoiding terrorism) to the product the government is offering; promotion is the communication of the value or advantage of avoiding terrorism executed by the government to the youths; and distribution in making government promises and products available and affordable to the youths and other citizens to enable them respond to the government efforts.

In summary, basic marketing tools include: product, price, promotion, place, process, people and physical evidence (Kotler and Keller, 2006).

Concept of Terrorism

Terrorism is synonymous to violent application of attacks against lives and properties for the purpose of creating fear among the people.

Terrorism can best be described as the calculated use of violence to create a general climate of fear in the population, and thereby realize a particular political objective (Jenkins, 2024). Terrorism is not restricted to pronounced criminals. Terrorism has also been perpetrated by political organizations with both rightist and leftist objectives, by nationalistic and religious groups, by revolutionaries, and even by state institutions such as armies, intelligent services and the Police (Jenkins, 2024)

The origin of terrorism has seen traced to 1790's as the terror used during the French Revolution by the revolutionaries against their opponents. Then, the Jacobin Party of Maximilian Robespierre carried out a reign of terror involving mass executions by the guillotine (Russel et al., 2009). Although this nature of terrorism then describes an act of violence by the state against its domestic enemies, but subsequently the act or terrorism has seen applied most frequently to violence aimed either directly or indirectly at governments with the aim of influencing government policies or toppling an existing government (Russel et al., 2009). Modern day terrorism is cloned with political influence. This is because, terrorism has been seen as synonymous to power, the pursuit of power, the acquisition of power and the use of power to achieve political change (Russell et al., 2009). Based on the association of terrorism with political power, a terrorist group might see itself as a freedom fighter, while the government and other people at the receiving end of the terrorist activities will perceive them to be terrorist. For

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instance, Osama Bin Laden was perceived by the Western Nations as a terrorist that must be punished, while some other countries in the Middle East and even Africa see him as a hero in the fight against Western operations (Oladimeji, 2019). However, since terrorism leads to destruction of lives and properties, it is not in any way a justifiable course and no nation is immune from the deadly act of terrorism.

Terrorism has manifested in many Africa countries such as Tunisia, Kenya, Tanzania, Morocco, Angola, Sudan, Niger, Liberia, Congo and even Nigeria. In Nigeria, some ethnic groups such as Niger Delta Peoples Volunteer Force (NIDPV), Niger Delta Youth Congress, Movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASOB), Independent people of Biafra (IPOB), Eastern Security Network (ESN), Odua People's Congress (OPC), and Boko Haram among others have existed and accused of terrorist activities. Boko Haram are operating in the North-Eastern part of Nigeria including Borno, Yobe and Adamawa where their deadly activities have claimed many lives and forced many citizens to the internally displaced persons camps (Olamide, 2019).

Causes of Terrorism in Nigeria

Some of the causes of terrorism in Nigeria as identified by Olamide (2019); Egeh and Dankofa (2019); and Ezeajughu (2021) include:

1. **Bad Governance:** A government that is selfish and does not have the interest of the people in the heart through their actions.

2. **Religious Extremism:** This is terrorism based on promotion and protection of religious belief.
3. **Proliferation of small arms and light weapons:** This is the increasing number of arms production and circulation in Nigeria through many sources including Quasi-security agencies.
4. **Foreign Influence:** Most of the terrorist-turned groups are affiliated to foreign organizations who sponsor the terrorist group for their stated reasons.
5. **Political Greed:** Some of the terrorist activities and groups are sponsored by politicians for their political interests. Some politicians hide under religion, secretly sponsor the terrorist group while claiming to be fighting the same cause with them.
6. **Ethnic Extremism:** Some of the terrorist group rose through fighting for the protection and promotion of their ethnic interest.
7. **Economic Extremism:** Members of the terrorist group belong to the group because they don't have any means of livelihood and because of the huge amount of money paid by the sponsors of the terrorist group, and the money the terrorist make themselves through their activities such as: Kidnapping, mining and drug trafficking.

Theoretical Framework Strain Theory

This theory is popularly referred to as the theory of "Anomie". The Theory was developed by Robert Merton in 1930. The theory defines "Anomie" as 'a social and psychological condition

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where norms are absent, weak or in total conflict with prevailing circumstances in a given society'. This means that Anomie exist when there is a barrier between a legitimate goal and legal means of achieving that goal, and in other to overcome that barrier the individual resorts to defense mechanism. The implication of this theory is that the youths get involved in terrorism because they belief that they cannot realize their legitimate aspirations because the legitimate means of realizing their legitimate aspiration are lacking or not adequately provided by the government and relevant agencies (Madu, 2018). This theory is relevant to our study because it explains the reasons why youths allow themselves to be used as tools for terrorism despite the death penalty involved in it.

Empirical Review

Some published articles related to the topic under study were reviewed. The review is as follows.

Olademeji (2019) carried out a study titled "Terrorism in Nigeria: Causes, Consequences and Panacea". The article states that despite the enactment of the Terrorism Provision Act of 2011 that provided for the punishment of death for involvement in terrorist activities, some Nigeria's still engage in the act of terrorism. The paper examined the causes and impact of terrorism in the Nigeria state. The study is an empirical study with interview as data collection method. The result of the review shows that: the causes of terrorism include bad governance, religious extremism, proliferation of small and light weapons, foreign influence and political

greed; the act of terrorism have caused the death of many Nigeria; the social economic lives of Nigeria citizens have been Jeopardized; farmers can longer go to farm; schools are closed indefinitely thereby increasing hunger, poverty and unemployment. The study recommends that: the Nigeria government should provide good governance to the citizens, government should enact laws that could discourage ethnic and religious extremism, education of the citizens should be vigorously implemented, the military and other security agencies should be encouraged and provided with needed equipment and the government should work with neighboring countries such as Chad, Niger and Cameroon on how to tackle terrorism in Nigeria.

In a seminar study, Olalaye (2013) carried out a study title "Empowering youths for a crime free society: The case of Nigeria". The paper examined the roles of empowerment for youth as key to a crime-free society. The study employed descriptive research design. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from a sample of 450 respondents. The data collected was analyzed with the Chi-Square and T-test analysis. The findings include, that there is a significant relationship between youth empowerment and attitude to crime involvement; there is significant relationship between male and female involvement in crime. The study recommends that government empowerment programs should be structured and centered on a participatory approach; government's human capital investment should

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be centered on the youths, and that the government through its relevant agencies should reach out to the youths regardless of their ethnic, cultural, religious, geographical or political affiliation.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Data obtained from the respondents were analyzed with descriptive statistics. The result of the analysis are as follows.

Age of Respondents

The result of the data analysis shows that 75% of the respondents are less than 20 years of age, 65.0% are between 21 – 30 years of age, 19.0% are between 31-40 years age, 19.0 % are between 31-40 years of age, while 8.1% are above 40 years. The implication of the analysis above is that over 84.0% of those interviewed in the correctional center fall within the ages of 21-40 years. This age range represents the youth of the country. The assumption is that a seminar percentage of youth are still vulnerable to the crimes that would either lead them to be reminded in the correctional centers or to death. This is most dangerous to the country and calls for immediate attention and action by all that could be involved as reliable change agents.

Gender of Respondents

The result of the data analysis shows that 87.4% of the respondents are of the male gender, while 12.6% are of the female. The surprise here is that though their number is small, but why will the female also be involved in serious crimes that would lead them to be reminded in the correctional centers.

Marital Status

The result of analysis shows that 7.9% of the respondents are married, 54.4% are single, 8.4% are separated, 16.7% are divorced, 10.5% are widows, while 2.1% are widower. This means that about 62.8% are either single or separated thereby giving them the opportunity to live unguided lifestyle

Educational Qualification

The result of the data analysis shows that 50.1% of the respondents have less than ordinary level as their educational qualification, 8.4% have ordinary level educational qualification, 4.2% have diploma or professional certificates, another 8.4% are undergraduates, 5.0% are graduates, 3.8% post graduates, while 20.1% have no educational qualification. This means that the literacy level of respondents is very low, hence the need for education.

Reasons for Involvement in Terrorist Activities

The result of the data analysis shows that 21.6% of the respondents claim they are involved in terrorists activities because of peer group influence, 14.6% claim poverty and economic hardship, 8.4% claim high cost of education, 12.6% claim unemployment, 22.6% claim weak parental upbringing, another 12.6% claim insecurity in the country, while 16.6% claim religious and ethnic belief.

This result is really disturbing because it proves that almost every facet of the country's social economic status has a serious problem. Since week parental upbringing is most prominent in the reasons for involvement in terrorist

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activities, education of the child should be given most concern.

Knowledge that the consequences of involvement in terrorism is death and life imprisonment

The result of the data analysis shows that 13.0% of the respondents have knowledge that the consequences of involvement in terrorism is death or life imprisonment, why 87.0% do not have the knowledge.

Rate of satisfaction for involvements in Terrorist activities

The result of the data analysis shows that 37.7% of the respondents claim they have very high satisfaction, 41.8% claim their satisfaction is high, 8.4% claim they are not sure of their level of satisfaction, 7.5% claim it is very low, while another 2.1% claim no satisfaction at all. The response of high level of satisfaction portrays extremism and lack of the knowledge of the consequences of terrorism. This requires greater efforts in educating the youths.

Other crimes committed by the respondents

The result of the data analysis shows that 25.1% of the respondents claim they have been involved in armed robbery and Brigandage, 27.2% claim they have been involved in kidnapping and assassination, 12.6% claimed they have been involved in stealing and theft, 8.4% claim they have been involved in house breaking and burglary, 18.8% claimed they have been involved in drugs and arms peddling, while 7.9% claimed

they have been involved in other crimes such as rape, cultism, arson and vandalization of government properties.

Occupation before involvement and arrest for terrorism

The result of the analysis of data obtained from the respondents shows that 58.6% of the respondents were unemployed before their involvement and arrest for terrorism, 8.4% were undergraduate or students, 25.1% civil or public servant, while 7.9% were self-employed. This result shows that unemployment is the major reasons for involvement in terrorism and other criminal activities.

Willingness to repent from terrorist activities if given the opportunity

From the result of analysis on the willingness of respondents to stop and repent from terrorism, 12.1% of the respondents said yes, 25.15 said no, while 62.8% said they are not yet sure.

Nationality of Respondents

From the result of analysis on the nationality of respondents, 67.0 of the respondents claim they are Nigerians, 23.0% claim they are from other African countries, while 10.0% claim they are not sure of their nationality.

Summary of Findings

From the literature review and analysis of data, the following findings emerged.

1. Both male and female youths are involved in terrorist activities, but the male are more in number.
2. Most of the youths involved in terrorist activities have less than ordinary level education.

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3. The main causes of youth's involvement in terrorism are: peer group influence, poverty, high cost of acquiring education, unemployment, weak parental upbringing, insecurity in the country, religious and ethnic extremism.
4. Most of those involved in terrorism do not have knowledge of the consequences of the crime.
5. Some of those involved in terrorism are indigenes of neighboring African countries.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, this study recommends a Marketing Model that comprise a sequence of marketing activities. This steps are as represented in the diagram below.

Table 2.1 Showing Marketing Model for eradicating youths' involvement in terrorism.

Explanation of the model

❖ Need Identification

- ❖ This means identifying the nature and needs of the Target Adopters (Youths). This further means identifying the reasons why youths get involved in terrorism and also the need to eradicate youths involvement in terrorism based on the consequences. The reasons why youths get involved in terrorism has earlier been summarized as peer group influence, poverty, high cost of acquiring education, unemployment, weak parental upbringing, insecurity in the country, religious and ethnic extremism. Also, the consequences of youth's involvement in terrorism is death of the youths and other citizens, and destruction of life and properties of all.

❖ Product Design

Product in this regard means social products. Social products comprise of all tangible and intangible offers by the relevant government agencies to prevent youth's involvement in terrorism. These products include;

- Provision of formal education to degree level for the youths at zero or minimal cost.
- Implementation of entrepreneurial education to provide the needed skills for the youths to be self-employed and further contribute to the economic development of the country.
- Provide enabling business and investment environment for the youths.

❖ Product Promotion

- This means Promotion of the social products by relevant Change Agents through

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appropriate promotion media such as Social Media, Digital Media, Military and Police Public Relations Officers, Seminars and Workshops by relevant Government Agencies.

❖ Product Delivery

❖ This requires that government must show physical evidence of her efforts aimed at implementing the Social Products for the purpose of preventing youth's involvement in terrorism.

❖ Monitoring and Evaluation

This requires that the implementation of the Social Product aimed at prevention or eradication of youth's involvement in terrorism must be closely monitored to ensure that the needed result is achieved, and appropriate corrections made when necessary.

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